

MAIN REQUIREMENTS THAT MUST BE USED IN THE DESIGN OF MODERN MEDIUM AND MULTI-STORY RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS IN THE CITY.

Bekturdiyev I.M.

(UrSU) Teacher.

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Annotation: In this article, the important issues in the design of medium and high-rise residential buildings in urban planning are suggested.

Key words: residential buildings, middle floor, high-rise, intermediate distances.

For many years, not a single high-rise building was built in our Republic. In recent years, the image of our country has been radically renewed. On the initiative of the head of our state, dozens of modern, earthquake-resistant and energy-efficient multi-storey houses have been built in each region. There are specific requirements and norms for the construction of multi-story and medium-story residential buildings. One of the most urgent issues today is maintaining the distance between residential buildings. Based on the conditions of Uzbekistan, the intermediate distances between medium and high-rise residential buildings were proposed as follows:

Distances between 3-story residential buildings

the picture above shows the dimensions of opposite, horizontal and vertical locations of the ribbon-shaped 3-story residential buildings.

Distances between 4-story residential buildings

the picture above shows the dimensions of opposite, horizontal and vertical locations of the ribbon-shaped 4-story residential buildings.

Distances between 5-story residential buildings

the picture above shows the dimensions of opposite, horizontal and vertical locations of the ribbon-shaped 5-story residential buildings.

Distances between 3-5-story residential buildings

the picture above shows the dimensions of opposite, horizontal and vertical locations of the ribbon-shaped 3-5-story residential buildings.

Distances between 7-story residential buildings

the picture above shows the dimensions of opposite, horizontal and vertical locations of the ribbon-shaped 7-story residential buildings.

Distances between 9-story residential buildings

the picture above shows the dimensions of opposite, horizontal and vertical locations of the ribbon-shaped 9-story residential buildings.

Distances between 9-5-story residential buildings

the picture above shows the dimensions of opposite, horizontal and vertical locations of the ribbon-shaped 9-5-story residential buildings.

Multi-apartment residential buildings must be designed in accordance with these standards. The compositional and architectural solutions of residential houses should take into account the principles of energy saving and energy efficiency, provide comfortable conditions for living, and connection with adjacent green areas. Non-building areas, two-way open pedestrian and car passages can be provided for the aeration of yard spaces. In this case, living quarters should be separated from transit. From the first floors, according to the urban planning project, there are exits to the plots of land belonging to the apartments (20-50 m²).

In the development of urban planning, it is appropriate to build multi-family residences, taking into account these proposals, in order to create comfort for people and ensure their safety. In addition, it would be very convenient for project organizations to place parking spaces, two types of children's playgrounds, recreation areas for the elderly and other elements between residential buildings by strictly observing these distances.

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